

TECHNOLOGY FOR PRODUCING LOW-SULFUR COKE FROM PETROLEUM RESIDUAL PRODUCTS

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Abstract. The current state and development prospects of low-sulfur petroleum coke production technology based on the thermal processing of heavy petroleum residues have been analyzed. The influence of feedstock composition, technological parameters of the coking process, and the physicochemical properties of the raw material on product quality and yield in the production of low-sulfur coke has been highlighted. The research results demonstrate that this technology plays an important role in the efficient processing of petroleum residues, the production of high-quality import-substituting coke, and the increase of the depth of petroleum refining.

Keywords: petroleum residues, low-sulfur coke, delayed coking, thermal cracking, feedstock quality, petroleum coke.

Development of deep petroleum refining technologies and the production of high value-added products from heavy petroleum residues are among the key strategic priorities of the modern petroleum refining industry. In particular, the steadily increasing demand for low-sulfur petroleum coke in the aluminum, metallurgical, and electrotechnical industries has significantly enhanced the scientific and practical importance of producing this material from locally available feedstocks.

The coking of heavy petroleum residues is based on the thermal conversion of high-molecular-weight hydrocarbons, resulting in the production of solid carbonaceous material (petroleum coke) together with valuable distillate fractions, including gasoline, gas oil, and gaseous products. This technology contributes to increasing the depth of crude oil processing, reducing the amount of heavy residual fractions, and improving the economic efficiency of refining through enhanced production of high-quality motor fuels [1; 63-b.].

The composition and physicochemical properties of the feedstock are among the most critical factors affecting the production of low-sulfur petroleum coke. Atmospheric and vacuum distillation residues, vacuum residue, pyrolysis tar, catalytic cracking residues, and aromatic-rich hydrocarbon fractions are considered suitable feedstocks for obtaining high-quality petroleum coke. Feedstock density, carbon residue, and sulfur content are the principal technological parameters determining both coke yield and product quality.

Technological flow diagram of a delayed coking unit with unheated coking chambers:

1, 6, 12–15 – Pumps; 2, 3 – Tubular furnaces; 4 – Feed tank (receiver); 5, 5' – Delayed coking chambers (coke drums); 7 – Four-way switching valve; 8, 19, 21 – Air coolers; 9 – Fractionating (distillation) column; 10, 11 – Stripping columns (steam strippers); 16 – Cooler; 17 – Separator; 18, 20 – Heat exchangers.

The delayed coking unit under consideration has an annual designed capacity of 600 thousand tons. The facility comprises four coking chambers, two tubular heating furnaces, a fractionation block, as well as a reactor complex equipped with heat recovery and final product cooling systems.

In the process, feedstock consisting of tar, thermal cracking residues, or their mixtures is used. The feedstock is divided into two parallel streams by pump No. 1 and directed to the lower and upper radiant tubes of tubular furnaces No. 2 and No. 3. After being heated to 350–380 °C, the material is introduced into the lower section of fractionation column No. 9, specifically to the upper cascade tray zone. Simultaneously, the high-temperature gas-vapor mixture generated in the operating coking chambers (No. 5) is also fed into the same section of the column.

Within the column, a counter-current heat and mass transfer process occurs between the upward-moving vapor-gas stream and the downward-flowing heated feedstock. Heavy fractions contained in the vapor phase condense and dissolve into the liquid stream, resulting in the formation of a secondary feed enriched with condensed components at the bottom of the column. Light fractions, in turn, vaporize and rise toward the upper section of the column.

The secondary feed withdrawn from the bottom of the column is pumped by pump No. 6 back to the convection section and radiant tubes of furnaces No. 2 and No. 3, which function as a reaction coil system. In this section, the feedstock is heated to 490–510 °C. To prevent coke deposition inside the tubes, superheated steam amounting to approximately 3% of the feed mass is injected as a turbulator. This increases flow turbulence, enhances heat transfer, and reduces the likelihood of coke formation on the tube walls. If necessary, steam may also be directed to separation columns No. 10 and No. 11.

The vapor-liquid mixture leaving the furnaces is directed via four-way valves (No. 7) into two parallel operating coking chambers. At the same time, the remaining two chambers are prepared for the next cycle. The heated feed enters the chambers from the bottom and gradually fills them. The chambers typically have an internal diameter of 4.6–5.5 m and a height of 27–28 m. Due to prolonged residence time, deep thermal cracking reactions occur inside the chambers. The

generated vapors are continuously withdrawn from the top and returned to fractionation column No. 9, while the heavy liquid residue remains in the chamber and gradually undergoes carbonization to form petroleum coke [4; 38-39 b.].

In fractionation column No. 9, the coking products are separated into individual fractions. Benzene vapors, water vapor, and coker gas are removed from the top of the column. These streams are first cooled in air cooler No. 8 and subsequently in water cooler No. 16, after which they are sent to separator No. 17. In the separator, the mixture is divided into water condensate, unstable gasoline, and wet gas fractions.

A portion of the unstable gasoline is returned by pump No. 15 to the top of the column as reflux. The remaining portion is passed through heat exchanger No. 18, where it is heated using the heat of light gas oil, and then sent to the stabilization unit. The water condensate separated in unit No. 17 is pumped by pump No. 14 through heat exchanger No. 20 and subsequently directed to steam superheaters located in the convection section of furnaces No. 2 and No. 3.

Light and heavy gas oils obtained from separation columns No. 10 and No. 11 are pumped by pumps No. 13 and No. 12, respectively, and passed through heat exchanger No. 18, where they serve as a heating medium for unstable gasoline. The streams are then directed to heat exchanger No. 20 for condensate heating. In the final stage, the gas oil fractions are cooled in air coolers No. 19 and No. 21 and sent to storage tanks.

At the end of the coking cycle, chambers filled with coke are taken out of service. Steam purging is carried out to remove residual liquid hydrocarbons and vapors. The recovered products are directed to fractionation column No. 9. When the coke temperature decreases to 400–405 °C, the vapor stream is sent to receiver No. 4. Steam purging continues until the coke temperature drops to 200 °C.

In the final step, cooling water is introduced into the chamber. Cooling continues until steam generation ceases and liquid water is observed in the drainage line connected to receiver No. 4. After complete cooling, the formed petroleum coke is removed from the chambers using hydraulic cutting equipment operating at a water pressure of List of References

This technological scheme enables deep thermal processing of heavy petroleum residues, ensuring the production of high-quality low-sulfur petroleum coke along with valuable distillate products such as gasoline, gas oil, and gas. The integration of heat recovery systems reduces energy consumption,

increases product yield, and improves the overall economic efficiency of the process.

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